

Analysis of Country-Specific Score-Card on the Multi-actor Community of Practice in the UPSCALE Project

Mulupi D.K¹, Aila F.O², Ombok B.O², Odhiambo D.G³

¹Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, Maseno University

²Department of Business Administration, Maseno University

³Department of Accounting and Finance, Maseno University

⁴Department of Crop and Soil Sciences, Maseno University

Abstract

The UPSCALE project is promoting the adoption and upscaling of Push-Pull Technology (PPT) with an objective of enhancing food productivity. The PPT farming system involves intercropping fodder crops and cereal crops to control *Striga* weed and fall armyworm. The pests have significantly reduced cereal productivity in EA. This farming system has other qualitative and quantitative benefits, such as protecting soil structures, controlling soil erosion, improving soil fertility, and producing animal feeds. However, despite the benefits, the adoption of the PPT farming system has been lower than expected in most of the implementing countries. There is still low seed production, and aggregation is still low. Therefore, reflecting the discussions in the annual general meeting and MAC meetings, a need to evaluate the progress of the project arose. A tool was rolled out through country coordinators to collect data through an online survey across the 5 countries. The finding shows that the main challenges experienced are inadequate *Desmodium* seed, PPT farming is labor-intensive, and the issues of disadoption. The UPSCALE project team has put in place strategies to address these challenges, including the use of cuttings and seedling production for farmers. It is expected that more farmers will continue adopting PPT farming, and at the end of the project, there will be a sustainable demand for PPT products for sustainability and scaling.

Keywords:

UPSCALE project, Push-Pull Technology (PPT), Score-Card, Multi-actor Community (MAC), Maseno University (MU)

INTRODUCTION

The UPSCALE project has been implemented in Eastern Africa with the primary goal of promoting the adoption and scaling of PPT as a sustainable farming practice (Drinkwater et al., 2021; *icipe*, 2015; Khan et al., 2008, 2018). PPT is an innovative, climate-smart approach that integrates fodder and cereal crops, as well as high-value vegetables. The technology is designed to address critical challenges in smallholder farming systems, particularly the management of pests and weeds that constrain productivity (Khan et al., 2011; Mirti, 2019; Nyangau et al., 2018).

Figure 1: *Striga* weed and fall army worm; Source; (*icipe*, 2015) https://www.push-pull.net/planting_for_prosperity.pdf

The typical PPT system involves establishing *Brachiaria* grass on the borders of cereal crop fields and planting *Desmodium* fodder legumes between the crop rows. This strategic design functions through a “push-pull” mechanism where *Brachiaria* acts as an attractive trap crop for pests such as the fall armyworm, while *Desmodium* repels them, thereby protecting the cereal crop as presented in Figure 1 (Chidawanyika et al., 2023; Fischler, 2010; Khan et al., 2011).

Figure 2: Push-Pull technology: source (Abate et al., 2024); <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1125471824000124>

In addition, PPT effectively suppresses the parasitic weed *Striga*, which has long plagued cereal farmers in the region. Beyond pest and weed control, the system generates multiple co-benefits, including improved livestock feed supply, soil fertility enhancement through biological nitrogen fixation, and reduced soil degradation due to ground cover (Chidawanyika et al., 2023; Drinkwater et al., 2021; *icipe*, 2015; *ICIPE*, 2011; Niassy et al., 2022).

Despite these well-documented advantages, adoption rates of PPT have remained relatively low, and in some cases, instances of disadoption have been observed. This raises important questions about the barriers hindering sustained uptake and the contextual factors that shape farmers' decisions. To address these concerns, the UPSCALE project, particularly under Work Package 1, has emphasized the need for comprehensive stakeholder assessments. These assessments are critical in understanding how farmers, extension services, policymakers, and other actors perceive the performance of PPT, and in identifying the strategies required to strengthen adoption, ensure sustainability, and scale the technology across diverse agro-ecological and socio-economic settings in Eastern Africa.

METHODOLOGY

The study design

Based on the stakeholders' engagement and discussions from WP1 in the UPSCALE project, the need to evaluate the progress of the country-specific MACs emerged. A questionnaire was developed by MU and shared with the country coordinators. An online survey was conducted using the questionnaire to collect data on the progress of the UPSCALE project. The data was collected from the stakeholders involved in the PPT products value chain. This included the extension officers, agro dealers, financial institutions, researchers, farmers, transporters, and companies, among others. The data that was collected included the description of the status for key challenges, identification of key required steps, specification of what UPSCALE is doing to address the steps, information on the expectations of the project at the end and after the project, outlining sociological and institutional MACs profile, information on what the country MACs have achieved or enabled, assessment of MACs effectiveness, steps ahead within UPSCALE timeframe, and outlining the way forward/expected MACs sustainability. The information collected was validated in the discussions at the specific country MAC meetings. The scorecard was then aligned with the

country-specific progress in all the aspects investigated through the discussion among the national MAC members.

The study area

A survey was conducted in five countries participating in the UPSCALE project. The countries include Kenya, Ethiopia, Uganda, Tanzania, and Rwanda. The map of the countries is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 3: Study area map; source:

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326293832/figure/fig1/AS:669416220016665@1536612672730/Map-of-Africa-showing-countries-Ethiopia-Uganda-Kenya-Rwanda-and-Tanzania-where-ppt-farming-has-been-implemented>

RESULTS

Country-Specific Score-Card

ISSUE	KENYA	RWANDA	TANZANIA	UGANDA	ETHIOPIA
Description of status for key challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Mismatch between demand and supply of <i>Desmodium</i> seeds. -Slow uptake of seed production and supply by private enterprises. -High seed cost due to reliance on imports (\$40/kg). -Limited mainstreaming of PPT into the national extension system; dissemination left to research organisations. -Underfunded extension services with few staff; low farmer access. -Slow scaling: PPT adoption remains on small plots with limited benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Resistance to new technologies among farmers. -Climate change/drought challenges. -High initial costs for establishing PPT. -Shortage of nurseries and seed merchants. -Poor tracking/quality assurance of <i>Desmodium</i> and <i>Brachiaria</i> seeds. -Low accessibility (affordability/availability) of inputs. -Lack of regulations in the PPT inputs market. -Pests, diseases, and post-harvest losses. -Lack of markets for PPT products. -Limited guidance on crop rotation with PPT. -Small land sizes. -Weak integration into the Crop Intensification Program (CIP). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Unfavourable weather conditions for <i>Desmodium</i> seed production. -Inadequate <i>Desmodium</i> seed supply. -Lack of streamlined marketing channels for seeds/companion plants. -Free grazing damages PPT plots. -Inadequate farmer knowledge of PPT benefits. -Farmers use unsuitable pesticides to control FAW. -Limited NGO involvement in seed production. -Silver-leaf <i>Desmodium</i> produces seeds but is not climate-smart; Green-leaf <i>Desmodium</i> is climate-smart but produces no seeds locally. -Low youth interest in PPT. -Small plot sizes (<1 acre). -Financial and capital constraints. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> --High costs of <i>Desmodium</i> and hybrid maize seeds. -Labour-intensive nature of PPT. -Preference for pesticides over PPT. -Free grazing (goats) destroys PPT plots due to weak by-laws. -PPT adoption not at scale. -Crop rotation challenges (PPT incompatible with certain crops like sweet potato). -Land tenure issues (hired/leased land reverted by owners). -PPT largely limited to demonstration plots. -Limited market for fodder from PPT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Labour-intensive PPT establishment. -Open grazing damages plots. -Difficult integration of PPT into crop rotation systems.
Key required steps identified.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Demonstrate dual demand for <i>Desmodium</i> (PPT + forage). -Facilitate registration and enable local production of <i>Desmodium</i> seeds in East Africa. -Empower farmer groups as seed merchants through community-based seed enterprises and cross-border exchanges. -Strengthen engagement with national/local governments to co-develop PPT extension strategies. -Adopt pluralistic extension approaches involving NGOs, churches, and other non-state actors. -Build capacity of extension workers and expand farmer access. -Expand PPT beyond small plots through farmer co-innovation, mechanisation, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Capacity building, awareness creation, demonstration of PPT benefits, cost-benefit analyses, market promotion, inclusion in schools and extension, engaging women and youth. -Introduce irrigation and climate-smart practices, promote resilient varieties, and sustainable land/forest management. -Local seed production with quality assurance, seed subsidies, VAT exemptions, partnerships across value chains, and stronger policy support. -Increase awareness, integrate PPT into existing nurseries, provide training, and engage women/youth in nursery production. -Create farmer demand, link farmers with seed agents, promote community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Produce seedlings in greenhouses and multiply seeds in suitable regions (e.g., Tanga). -Engage private companies, NGOs, and research bodies in seed production/marketing; promote cuttings; train lead farmers on QDS seed production. -Enforce by-laws against free grazing; provide alternative pasture; encourage fencing or zero-grazing. -Disseminate PPT knowledge via schools, NGOs, social media, and demo plots. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Promote community-based <i>Desmodium</i> and <i>Brachiaria</i> seed production, including vegetative propagation. -Increase awareness through radio, TV, roadshows, farmer exchanges, and extension campaigns. -Promote PPT for soil fertility, <i>Striga</i> control, fodder, and agroforestry integration. -Research and recommend compatible crops (legumes, vegetables) for crop rotation with PPT. -Reduce labour-intensity by fabricating simple mechanized tools for planting, weeding, and harvesting. -Sensitize farmers to reduce pesticide reliance; promote IPM and bio-pesticides. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Develop labour-saving tools and promote community labour-sharing schemes. -Increase awareness and demonstrate cost-effectiveness of PPT. -Improve grazing management practices. -Explore alternative companion plants and compatible crops. -Modify PPT systems to fit local contexts. -Promote adoption in low fertility areas and encourage use of PPT

	integration into crop intensification arrangements	seed production, conduct market surveys, use digital platforms, and engage women/youth. -Set production standards, create platforms for farmer-led multiplication, and establish selection criteria. -Increase local multipliers, subsidies, expand agro-dealers, promote cuttings/seedlings, and strengthen public-private partnerships. -Establish national PPT input market regulations. -Promote resistant varieties and wider adoption. -Train farmers on handling, provide storage facilities. -Promote fodder use, create demand, link livestock and PPT farmers, digitize fodder chains, and train on conservation. -Research suitable crops, train farmers, use demonstration plots, integrate recommendations into policies, and diversify PPT crops. -Promote land use consolidation, longer leases, adaptability studies, integration of livestock, multiple cropping, and soil fertility management. -Advocate for mainstreaming, adapt spacing guidelines, and strengthen <i>Desmodium</i> value chains.	-Train farmers on correct pesticide use and IPM. -Involve more NGOs in advocacy and seed production. -Reframe agriculture to attract youth (mindset change, incentives, and fodder value chains). -Encourage larger plots (≥ 0.2 ha), incentivise seed producers, and expand national <i>Desmodium</i> seed production. -Provide agricultural credit with flexible collateral (group guarantees, insurance). -Train farmers and extension staff in seed production principles. -Establish local knowledge hubs and village centres for seed distribution and marketing.	-Manage open grazing by linking PPT to fodder value chains (hay, pellets), encouraging by-laws, and sensitizing communities on feed policies. -Address land tenure by promoting longer-term lease agreements and group collateral arrangements. -Showcase large-scale PPT success stories to inspire scaling.	products for animal feeds.
What is UPSCALE doing to address them?	-The project has mapped the locations of existing and potential farmers/groups and input merchants, created village knowledge centres, and started the process of linking them to catalyse demand for <i>Desmodium</i> seed. -Through road shows and other dissemination efforts, PPT had been promoted to create demand. -The strategy to address the seed bottleneck has included: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Partnering with small and medium seed companies (Kenya Seed Company, Simlaw Seeds, and Advantage Crops). Promoting community-based seed production (reduced seed costs to ~€10/kg). 	-Different campaigns for awareness -Formation of farming groups. -Establishment of nurseries and demo plots. -Engagement of different stakeholders in the food system	-Sensitization programs, -Establishment and monitoring of PPT fields, -Training sessions for extension agents, researchers, and farmers, as well as stakeholder workshops and meetings to reinforce project activities and gather feedback. -Farmer field days and participation in national agricultural shows have been utilised for demonstrating PPT benefits.	-PPT training across selected value chains (maize, <i>Desmodium</i> , <i>Brachiaria</i> , vegetables) - <i>Desmodium</i> and <i>Brachiaria</i> grass seed/seedlings and/or planting materials provision for demonstration plots; encouraging vegetative propagation of <i>Desmodium</i> (Farmers in Bugiri, Busia, Tororo previously produced silver leaf <i>Desmodium</i> seeds for the region) -Awareness campaigns on PPT (benefits-improving soil fertility; control of <i>Striga</i> weed, soil cover, fodder for animals, promote agroforestry; establishment, management, enterprises, policies, etc.) through exhibitions, radio/TV shows, on-	-Provided training across the PPT value chain. -Supported dissemination of seeds. -Built farmer capacity through workshops and extension support.

	<p>3. Influencing <i>Desmodium</i> seed certification policy.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -We are engaging and co-developing Push-pull dissemination strategies with county governments to whom agricultural extension has been devolved. For example, the project has directly trained 53 Homabay County extension staff who are leading the expansion of the technology in all sub-counties. - The project has adopted a pluralistic extension strategy involving non-state actors, e.g., Ripple Effect, Justice & Mercy group, and church groups. The project is expanding access to PPT knowledge by building the knowledge and capacity of these extension partners. -Through other work packages, the project is expanding the applicability of PPT across multiple scales, adapting and co-innovating with farmers the appropriate agronomic practices that fit their contexts, and adapting their crop intensification arrangements to their needs. 			<p>farm demos, field days, dialogues, farmer-to-farmer extension services.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Stakeholder engagement- MACs, GA/RSM, review meetings, monitoring visits, knowledge sharing across borders, etc. -PPT demonstration plots have been set up in the study regions -Promotion of community <i>Desmodium</i> and <i>Brachiaria</i> seed production; promote vegetative propagation of <i>Desmodium</i> and <i>Brachiaria</i> (complementary project activities in Uganda) -Identifying and testing other compatible crops to the PPT system for intercropping and crop rotation, e.g., legumes, vegetables -Sensitise the community to understand PPT and its benefits, and the dangers of continually using pesticides 	
Expectations by project end	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -It is expected that local production of <i>Desmodium</i> through community-based seed production units will have been established, and seed supply matched to demand, prices reduced to < \$10 per kg, and <i>Desmodium</i> seed production and marketing enterprises will have sustainable business cases. -National and county governments will have included the PPT strategy as a key solution to agricultural production constraints, and appropriately allocated resources for its extension. -An increased number of non-state actors involved in the extension of PPT. A critical mass of secondary disseminators will have gained knowledge of PPT and will have sufficient capacity to independently scale up PPT. -PPT will have been adapted and further intensified across multiple scales, in a transdisciplinary process involving all value chain actors. The technology will have been optimised to fit with farmers' agronomic practices, agroecological contexts, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Have more farmers adopt the technology. -Have the project included in the National extension models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The Ministry of Agriculture will understand the benefits of PPT and incorporate it into the conservation agriculture policy document. =TARI -Knowledge disseminated to farmers, who will be empowered to adopt PPT, NGOs specializing in agriculture will contribute to technology dissemination and work with farmers and district councils to ensure long-term sustainability. LGAs, TOSCI, NGOs, farmers, private companies, agro dealers -That the youth is involved in PPT productions -Contribute to food and nutrition security attainment in Tanzania 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased production and productivity of maize under PPT -Increased adoption of PPT -Increased fodder production -Increased enterprise mix (crops/livestock mix) -Increased value addition and market access/strengthened linkages for PPT products -Increased awareness of PPT among various stakeholders, including farmers and policymakers -Increased stakeholder engagement in dissemination of PPT (<i>Desmodium</i> seed producers, livestock farmers, maize producers, etc.) -Increased soil fertility, reduced <i>Striga</i> seed load, reduced stem borer and FAW incidence and damage levels -Increased access to fodder 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Stakeholders within the value chain are empowered to participate in the dissemination of PPT knowledge

	production needs. Solutions for the wider scale applicability of PPT would have been initiated.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased availability and affordability of <i>Desmodium</i> seeds in Tanzania -Increased availability of fodder (<i>Desmodium</i> and <i>Brachiaria</i>) for livestock farmers -Promote <i>Desmodium</i> awareness to poultry keepers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased economic benefits (increased savings, reduced costs) from PPT -Increased food security -Increased access to (e-)extension services -Increased PPT demonstration farms at zonal agricultural research and development institutes (ZARDIs) (e.g., Kachwekano) 	
Expectations after the project ends	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Beyond the project aims for a self-sustaining <i>Desmodium</i> seed market to be established, with seed supply well matched to demand and prices stabilized. -Autonomous diffusion taking place even in the absence of UPSCALE project partners. National and county governments, as well as non-state actors, will have included the PPT strategy as a key solution to agricultural production constraints and adequately funded its extension. -PPT will have been adapted and further intensified across multiple scales, in a transdisciplinary process involving all value chain actors. The technology will have been optimised to fit with farmers' agronomic practices, agroecological contexts, and production needs. Solutions for the wider scale applicability of PPT would have been initiated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Have the PPT adopted -More propagandistic materials are available. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -PPT will continuously be implemented in the country (Increased number of PPT farmers) -Ready market for <i>Desmodium</i> fodder and seed, <i>Brachiaria</i>, and nappier grass in the project region -Promote <i>Desmodium</i> awareness to poultry keepers (PPT adopters are expected to sell increased egg volumes, up to 12-30 eggs for free-range chickens) -PPT adopters will have additional income streams, e.g., from selling local chicken eggs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Scaling in and out PPT -Stakeholder involvement -Increased soil fertility and reduced <i>Striga</i> and FAW damage -Increased food security. -Increased economic benefits of PPT -Increased community-based resilience to climate change -Sustainable community-based seed sources for <i>Desmodium</i> -Increased fodder sources -Increased responsiveness to innovations and agricultural technologies -Empowered farmer teachers -Increased level of satisfaction of project beneficiaries with PPT Increased PPT demonstration farms at zonal agricultural research and development institutes (ZARDIs) (e.g., Kachwekano) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Stakeholders have the expertise and resources to disseminate accurate information
Sociological and institutional MACs profile	-The Kenya MAC comprises institutions that are representative of different stakeholder interests, including international agricultural research, financial and agribusiness development Institutions, national research and extension, farmers' direct interest representation, farming systems advisory NGOs, women, youth, and persons living with disabilities, input suppliers, and insurance risk management agents.	MAC ranges from different stakeholders in the food system and value chain. Input supplies [seed producers, NGOs, agro-dealers, local government, aggregators, and farmers], Growers [farmers, cooperatives, researchers, NGOs], Marketers [farmers, collectors, wholesalers, processing companies, agro-dealers, transporters], The end user [farmer, consumers, researchers, government], Extension officers, Policy-makers, Financial institutions, Insurance companies.	-Government organisations (TARI, VIC, TOSCI and district councils, regional administration), non-governmental organisations (OWSL, MADEO, VIFAFIO, GRA, MALI, FRAT, TAHUCHA and MFEC), Agro-dealer (PONA), Financial institutions (CRDB and TCB), Faith-based organisations (A.CT and ELCT), and Farmers' representative	Actors in the agricultural sector in the country. They include members from the Ministry of Agriculture, non-government organizations- AUPWAE, One-acre Fund, micro-finance support centre, Agricultural extension systems, Civil society organizations, Agro-processors, M-Omulimisa, and farmer representatives.	-Encompasses representatives from governmental bodies such as the Ministry of Agriculture, non-governmental organisations including PELUM Ethiopia and PAN, agricultural research institutes, institutions of higher learning, financial institutions, and farmer representatives.

<p>What has the country MACs achieved or enabled</p>	<p>-The country MAC has enabled visibility and further expansion of PPT in western Kenya, and has enabled effective utilisation of fodder from PPT, thus demonstrating demand for <i>Desmodium</i> seeds, and supporting the emergence of a strong forage marketing network and linkages with the dairy industry, in which new communication media have been deployed. The Mac has also enabled the inclusion of other relevant value chain actors, e.g., grain aggregators, micro-finance institutions, and input merchants.</p>	<p>-Established dissemination and communication pathways for PPT awareness and adoption. -Expanded PPT across different agro-ecological conditions. -Enhanced farmer mobilization and sensitization. -Set up 14 training sites for farmers on PPT. -Reached 500+ farmers via roadshows and demo plots. -Supported two farmer groups to establish nurseries for <i>Brachiaria</i> and <i>Desmodium</i>. -Two farmer groups producing <i>Desmodium</i> vines and <i>Brachiaria</i> splits. -Expanded PPT to additional districts. -Over 400 farmers have adopted PPT. -Farmers sold over 4 tons of <i>Desmodium</i> and <i>Brachiaria</i>. -Engaged new stakeholders (e.g., Kenya Seed Company). -Participated in regional stakeholder meetings (RSM and GA). -Hosted a Ph.D. student for 8 months. -Strengthened knowledge through cross-learning visits to Tanzania.</p>	<p>-Upscaling PPT in the UPSCALE project, implementing areas and other nearby areas, -Creation of awareness on PPT, -Training of farmers and agricultural extension workers, -Establish KEH and village knowledge centres. National meetings and workshops were held for MAC members and other stakeholders. -Policy makers were sensitised on PPT, whereby acquired knowledge was used to encourage and advise farmers on the use of PPT.</p>	<p>-Popularisation of PPT as an approach for agro-ecological agri-food systems transformation -Awareness of the existence of relevant policies, strengths, and gaps among MAC members -Identified target areas for the introduction of PPT -Farmer sensitization on PPT through radio talk shows, etc. -Integration of PPT in our various institutions for wider dissemination -Free exchange of information and knowledge sharing on what works, challenges, and how to address the challenges -Many farmers are now adopting PPT as a farming practice</p>	<p>-Policy framework analysis -Farmer sensitization</p>
<p>Assessment of MAC effectiveness [3=very effective, 2=effective, 1=not effective]</p>	<p>-The MAC has been effective in expanding PPT beyond research. It has successfully facilitated multi-actor exchanges aimed at improving the technical performance of PPT, research impact, and suitability of dissemination strategies. Its broad representation has also ensured the inclusion of all stakeholder interests in formulating the research and development agenda, such that ownership and agency are built over the project phase to sustain activities beyond the project. 3=very effective</p>	<p>-MAC spreads information across areas and sets different mechanisms for integrating PPT in extension -University students researching PPT. 2=effective</p>	<p>-MAC facilitates the running of the project activities by giving advice, supervision, and monitoring. -MAC, as a part of the project, its members are involved in planning, implementation, and follow-up of all activities, which facilitates ownership of the project by farmers and other stakeholders within the project implementing area. It is from the above scenario that the process of upscaling the project technologies is simplified. 3=very effective</p>	<p>-We have visited PPT sites in Kamuli, Namutumba, Bugiri, Iganga, and assessed the level of PPT adoption and PPT performance against control plots; adoption of zero grazing (PPT has been integrated with Climate-Smart Agriculture); we provide sensitisation through farmer-teachers; selected schools to demonstrate PPT; <i>Desmodium</i> seed price is expensive, UGS160,000.00 per kilogramme. The MAC members need more facilitation to carry out the required activities 2=effective</p>	<p>-MAC members need to be empowered to contribute to project objectives without external dependence 2=effective</p>

Steps ahead within the UPSCALE timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Leveraging existing knowledge centres/ ATCs/Community centres/farmer teachers to expand the knowledge and practice of PPT; help in identifying and establishing more demonstration/ learning sites, translation and distribution of PPT materials in local languages; and monitoring and evaluating feedback from farmer communities and value chain actors. -Participate in developing and implementing upcoming dissemination activities, and further streamlining of dissemination efforts according to the most effective tools and optimised spatial targeting. -Participate in streamlining seed access and training access; matching farmers' needs to seed supply and training opportunities, and vice versa. -Strongly promote the uptake of UPSCALE's KEH and other project linkages beyond the current project cycle; mainstream Sustainable Intensification in regional and community policy and agricultural extension in strategic policy targeting. -Participate in specifically addressing identified adoption challenges - in training (incl. a new generation of trainers or retraining of trainers for these adaptations), e.g., multiple crops integration, flexible field sizes, crop rotation, intercropping, relay planting, or <i>Desmodium</i> nurseries, options for addressing free grazing issues (live fences, <i>Desmodium</i> nurseries, community agreements). -Participate in farmer recruitment, documentation, awareness raising, and leveraging the EAFF network of farmers, other value chain actors, and linking farmers to opportunities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -To increase farmers' mobilization to adopt the PPT technology -To engage more stakeholders to increase awareness and adoption of the technology -To expand PPT technology to other areas and districts of Rwanda -To encourage PPT nursery establishment in farmers' groups -To establish different channels of PPT information dissemination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Sensitization campaigns targeting farmers and stakeholders in districts beyond the project's implementation area. - Establishment of additional demonstration farms. -Conduct meetings and workshops for the management team, farmers, and stakeholders to reinforce PPT adoption. -Organise meetings with policymakers, the Ministry of Agriculture, and government administrators to highlight the PPTs' significance for upscaling agriculture. Identification of suitable areas for <i>Desmodium</i> seed production. -Scaling up PPT implementation in regions beyond the project's focus areas. -Establishment of more PPT intensification fields, along with monitoring and data collection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Demo Plots -Exhibitions and Roadshows -Develop print media material -Conduct radio and TV shows on PPT -Engage agro input dealers and seed producers to strengthen seed systems -Engage MACs on dissemination approaches -More frequent MAC meeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -More Demo plots -Public engagement -Value chain collaboration
Way forward/expected MACs sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Individual MAC members' sectoral connections can be leveraged for further reach beyond the project. The current MAC membership can redefine and formalise new roles beyond PPT UPSCALE. A present opportunity is expanding the commercialisation of PPT products, e.g., 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Sticking MAC to the national farming system and value chain, where the effect of pests has been witnessed. -Establish more trials to have evidence-based benefits for farmers to see the need for the technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identification and engagement of more MAC members, -Conduct workshops and meetings, -Site selection for <i>Desmodium</i> seed production, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Engage MACs on dissemination approaches -More frequent MAC meeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Diversify seed access and promote community seed production -Improve labour efficiency and promote collaboration

	<p>livestock fodder, and even expanding their opportunity in input production and distribution, e.g., of <i>Desmodium</i> seeds.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Make the seeds available and affordable for farmers -Policy that supports PPT to be formulated -Certification of the <i>Desmodium</i> seeds -Capacity building of the farmers to multiply the <i>Desmodium</i> seeds, link the producers to the market, and train the farmers on PPT skills -Integrate PPT in broader terminologies, such as regenerative agriculture as an IPM strategy to be part of the ongoing discussion on sustainable and resilient food systems. 	<p>-Engagement of a newly established non-governmental organisation that focuses on resilient agriculture, including PPT</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Enhance Awareness -Address livestock management challenges -Integrate PPT with existing farming systems -Leverage existing value chains and stakeholders -Ensure the sustainability of MACs -Expand outreach and dissemination efforts
Call to Action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Certification of <i>Desmodium</i> seeds -Increase desmodium seed production -Enhance the operations of MACs to other projects 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creation of <i>Desmodium</i> seed standards. - Training stakeholders on standards. - Multiplication of <i>Desmodium</i> seeds to increase availability. - Promotion of PPT integration in cereals and vegetables. - Incorporation of PPT into Conservation Agriculture Policy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Convene MAC meeting, streamline activities for accomplishment by MACs. Include a sustainability plan during the deliberations -Collaborate with EAFF to identify policy bottlenecks -Develop policy briefs -MACs require specific allocations for their activities 	

DISCUSSION

The results demonstrated that despite PPT being crucial in addressing pest, soil fertility, and fodder challenges, its adoption across the five countries faces systemic, institutional, and technical barriers. The countries struggle with the issues of *Desmodium* seed availability and affordability. Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, and Uganda report high costs as well as inadequate supply of *Desmodium* seeds. Over reliance on imported seeds in countries like Kenya and the absence of structured seed value chain in countries like Tanzania make adoption of PPT expensive for smallholders who are also the majority. Additionally, in these countries for instance Kenya and Uganda, PPT has not been effectively integrated into national extension systems.

The countries experience limited extension staff, underfunding, and reliance on NGOs or research institutions restrict farmer access to information and technical support. The resistance to new technologies in countries like Rwanda and the preference for pesticides in Uganda also contributes to low adoption of PPT. Low youth interest in PPT in Tanzania suggests sustainability challenges unless incentives for youth engagement are introduced. PPT's perennial nature complicates crop rotation in Ethiopia and Uganda. Small land sizes in Rwanda and Tanzania and tenure insecurity in Uganda further constrain integration. Free grazing is an issue in Tanzania, Uganda, and Ethiopia. Unfavourable weather in the region and climate change/drought threaten sustainability. Seed production also depends on specific agro-ecological conditions, complicating large-scale multiplication. Lack of regulations and weak integration into national programs especially in Rwanda and Kenya limit mainstreaming. Limited markets for PPT products in Rwanda and Uganda also reduce farmer incentives to adopt beyond subsistence use. The challenge of *Desmodium* seed availability in PPT farming has also been mentioned in the literature (*icipe*, 2009; Maina & Gowland-Mwangi, 2014).

However, UPSCALE is tackling common barriers across the region while tailoring solutions to country-specific contexts. A recurring challenge has been the *Desmodium* seed bottleneck. In Kenya and Uganda, significant progress has been made through partnerships with seed companies and community-based seed production, resulting in lower costs and improved availability. This model could be replicated in Rwanda, Tanzania, and Ethiopia, where shortages and inconsistent quality remain critical constraints. Rwanda and Tanzania have adopted the use of splits as an alternative to seedlings.

Extension and dissemination approaches differ across the region. Kenya has leveraged devolved county governments and pluralistic extension partnerships, which broaden reach and sustainability. Uganda's use of multi-channel communication such as radio, exhibitions, farmer-to-farmer extension to provide wide coverage, while Rwanda and Tanzania focus on nurseries, demo plots, and field days to drive farmer awareness. These approaches show that scaling PPT requires not just technical training but also farmer engagement platforms adapted to local systems.

Policy and institutional engagement has emerged as a crucial sector to support PPT farming. Kenya's progress in influencing seed certification policy shows how institutional reforms can unlock farmer-led seed systems. Uganda's stakeholder platforms such as MACs and GA/RSM also strengthen multi-actor collaboration, while Rwanda is integrating PPT into broader agricultural programmes. These examples highlight the importance of institutionalizing PPT beyond project boundaries. Socio-economic barriers such as labour demands, land tenure issues, and farmer perceptions remain unresolved in Ethiopia and Uganda. UPSCALE's adaptive responses such as promoting vegetative propagation, testing compatible crops, and linking PPT to soil fertility and fodder benefits are important steps, but wider adoption will require context-sensitive innovations that reduce labour intensity and fit smallholder farming logics. The expectations outlined suggest that UPSCALE aims to transition PPT from a project-driven initiative into a mainstream agricultural practice across East Africa. A central focus is on seed system sustainability. Ethiopia's model of community-based seed production, alongside private sector involvement, is expected to make seeds both affordable and accessible. If successful, this approach will be a blueprint for Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda, and Kenya, where seed bottlenecks remain a key barrier.

Policy integration is another major milestone. By embedding PPT into government strategies Kenya's county policies, Rwanda's national extension models, Tanzania's conservation agriculture policy, Uganda's research and development platforms, the technology moves from short-term promotion to long-term institutionalisation. This is critical for ensuring funding, legitimacy, and wide-scale adoption. Socio-economic benefits are strongly emphasised in Uganda and Tanzania, where PPT is expected to improve food security, reduce input costs, and diversify livelihoods through fodder and livestock integration. These expectations highlight PPT's potential not just as a pest-control technology but as a holistic farming system innovation that strengthens resilience, productivity, and incomes.

Kenya is positioned as a model for building a sustainable seed system, with a functioning *Desmodium* seed market and government/non-state actor integration into agricultural policies. This suggests long-term continuity even without donor support, as well as potential for large-scale adoption. Rwanda's progress shows that awareness creation is a central pillar for technology adoption. The emphasis on extension materials reflects the importance of knowledge dissemination in driving farmer uptake. Tanzania demonstrates both direct agricultural benefits and enterprise opportunities. The link between PPT adoption and poultry production in Kenya introduces new income streams, highlighting diversification and household-level resilience. The ready market for fodder and seed suggests an emerging agribusiness ecosystem around PPT. Uganda showcases a holistic integration of PPT, combining agronomic improvements like soil fertility, pest and weed reduction with socioeconomic outcomes such as income, food security, empowerment of farmer teachers, and climate resilience. This points toward long-term sustainability, particularly through community-based seed systems and ZARDI-led demonstrations. Ethiopia shows capacity building as the primary outcome, with stakeholders gaining the expertise needed to independently scale and disseminate PPT. This represents a critical institutional base for future expansion.

Kenya's MAC stands out for its inclusivity, particularly its explicit representation of marginalized groups including women, youth, and persons living with disabilities, as well as risk management agents like insurance companies. This suggests a deliberate effort to ensure social equity and resilience in agricultural transformation. Rwanda's MAC reflects a systems approach, mapping actors across the full food value chain from input suppliers to end users. This breadth allows for strong vertical and horizontal linkages, ensuring PPT is embedded not just in production but also in markets, policy, and consumption. Tanzania's MAC highlights the central role of government and NGOs, complemented by agro-dealers, faith-based organizations, and financial institutions. This structure suggests potential for strong institutional support and grassroots reach, though it may rely heavily on external actors for sustained farmer engagement. Uganda's MAC is notable for the integration of ICT-enabled extension alongside government and NGO actors. This digital component provides opportunities for scalable, cost-effective knowledge dissemination to farmers, while civil society and microfinance institutions enhance farmer empowerment and financial access.

The country MACs have played a critical catalytic role in scaling, institutionalizing, and contextualizing PPT within different agricultural and policy environments. In Kenya, the achievements reflect a market-driven approach where demand creation for *Desmodium* has triggered the development of a forage value chain linked to the dairy industry. The inclusion of financial institutions and microfinance agents shows progress towards sustainability through market and credit linkages. In Rwanda, MACs demonstrates strong grassroots mobilization and farmer engagement. The establishment of nurseries, farmer groups, and multiple dissemination channels shows local ownership and capacity building. Engagement with Kenya Seed Company and cross-country partnership also signal growing regional collaboration and commercialization potential. In Tanzania, the results highlight the institutional anchoring of PPT through KEHs, policy sensitization, and national-level workshops. Policymaker involvement increases the likelihood of PPT being embedded into national strategies, though the heavy reliance on workshops and meetings suggests that farmer-level adoption needs continued strengthening. In Uganda, the MAC's strength lies in policy awareness, integration, and knowledge sharing. The use of mass media and institutional platforms has widened reach, while farmer adoption is growing. However, ensuring continuity beyond project interventions will require stronger local seed systems and extension mechanisms. While Ethiopia's progress seems more limited compared to other countries, the emphasis on policy analysis and farmer sensitization lays a foundation for future institutionalization. Strengthening practical adoption and building local seed systems will be critical next steps.

CONCLUSION

The UPSCALE project has made significant strides in addressing the challenges limiting the adoption and sustainability of PPT across Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda, and Ethiopia. Through interventions such as seed system strengthening, awareness creation, training, stakeholder engagement, and policy influence, the project has demonstrated the potential of PPT to enhance food security, soil fertility, pest management, and livestock fodder supply. The establishment of country-level MACs has been central in facilitating dissemination, promoting policy dialogue, strengthening value chains, and ensuring wider reach and ownership of the technology.

Despite these achievements, sustainability remains dependent on addressing structural and institutional barriers. These include limited seed availability and affordability, weak extension services, inadequate policies, and slow farmer uptake due to high labor requirements, land constraints, and free grazing practices. Looking forward, embedding PPT into national agricultural systems, improving seed systems, engaging private enterprises, and fostering policy reforms are crucial to ensure that PPT scales beyond pilot sites to become a transformative and climate-smart agricultural solution across the region.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Develop and implement national seed certification standards for *Desmodium* and *Brachiaria*, promote community-based seed production, and incentivize private sector engagement to ensure affordability and availability.
2. Mainstream PPT into national and regional agricultural policies, extension programs, and conservation agriculture strategies to secure long-term adoption and funding.
3. Train extension officers, farmer-teachers, and non-state actors, while leveraging local knowledge centres and digital platforms to scale awareness and adoption.
4. Strengthen MACs by ensuring regular meetings, resource allocation, and integration of diverse stakeholders including youth, women, financial institutions, and agro-dealers for sustainability.
5. Support continuous research on crop rotation, intercropping options, and climate-smart adaptations of PPT to fit diverse agro-ecological and socio-economic contexts, while monitoring adoption impacts on food security and livelihoods.

Acknowledgement

We thank all the UPSCALE country coordinators for the effort shown in reaching out to the MACs to provide the information for the study.

Funding statement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 861998.

References

- Abate, M., Atnafu, G., Alemu, B., Alameneh, Y., Molla, A., Tadesse, M., & Gebremariam, G. (2024). Evaluation of push-pull technology for pest and soil fertility management on maize in north western Ethiopia. *Italian Journal of Agronomy*, 19(2), 100012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijagro.2024.100012>
- Chidawanyika, F., Muriithi, B., Niassy, S., Ouya, F. O., Pittchar, J. O., Kassie, M., & Khan, Z. R. (2023). Sustainable intensification of vegetable production using the cereal ‘ push - pull technology ’: benefits and one health implications. *Environmental Sustainability*, 0123456789. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42398-023-00260-1>
- Drinkwater, L. E., Midega, C. A. O., Awuor, R., Nyagol, D., & Khan, Z. R. (2021). Perennial legume intercrops provide multiple belowground ecosystem services in smallholder farming systems. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 320, 107566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107566>
- Fischler, M. (2010). Impact assessment of push – pull technology developed and promoted by *icipe* and partners in eastern Africa. In *Digital Processes. icipe*. (2009). *Impact Assessment of Push-Pull Technology Developed and Promoted By. icipe*. (2015). The ‘ Push – Pull ’ Farming System : Climate-smart , sustainable agriculture for Africa. In *The ‘Push–Pull’ Farming System: Climate-smart, sustainable agriculture for Africa*. http://www.push-pull.net/planting_for_prosperity.pdf
- ICIPE. (2011). Climate-smart push–pull: resilient, adaptable conservation agriculture for the future. *International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology*, 1–8.
- Khan, Z., Amudavi, D., & Pickett, J. (2008). Push-Pull Technology Transforms Small Farms in Kenya. *PAN North America Magazine*, 20–21.
- Khan, Z., Midega, C., Pittchar, J., Pickett, J., & Bruce, T. (2011). Push-pull technology: A conservation agriculture approach for integrated management of insect pests, weeds and soil health in Africa. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 9(1), 162–170. <https://doi.org/10.3763/ijas.2010.0558>
- Khan, Z., Pittchar, J., Midega, C., & Pickett, J. (2018). Push-Pull Farming System Controls Fall Armyworm: Lessons from Africa. *Outlooks on Pest Management*, 29, 220–224. https://doi.org/10.1564/v29_oct_09
- Maina, S. W., & Gowland-Mwangi, J. (2014). *International Journal of Agricultural Extension INNOVATING ORGANIZATIONAL SYSTEMS OF AGRICULTURAL EXTENSION IN*. 02(01), 57–66.
- Mirti, I. U. (2019). *Analysis of the Impact of Push-Pull Technology on Household Food Security and Nutrition in Eastern Uganda and Western Kenya Table of Contents*. 0–32.
- Niassy, S., Agbodzavu, M. K., Mudereri, B. T., Kamalongo, D., Ligowe, I., Hailu, G., Kimathi, E., Jere, Z., Ochatum, N., Pittchar, J., Kassie, M., & Khan, Z. (2022). Performance of Push–Pull Technology in Low-Fertility Soils under Conventional and Conservation Agriculture Farming Systems in Malawi. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(4), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14042162>
- Nyangau, I. M., Kelboro, G., Hornidge, A., & Midega, C. A. O. (2018). *Stakeholders Interaction and Social Learning : The Case of Push-Pull Technology Implementation for Stemborer Pest Control in Ethiopia. October*. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints201810.0480.v1>